

РАЗДЕЛ 1. БИОЛОГИЯ

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BIOTRANSFORMATION OF NUTRIENTS IN THE BODY OF PRIMATES

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Abstract: The article scientifically substantiates the effectiveness of the use of biologically active additives in the diets of primates and experimentally confirms their positive effect on the bioconversion of diets. The coefficients of digestibility of diets using fishmeal and dry chlorella in their structures are determined. Since, one of the main factors that have a strong effect on the metabolism and energy processes occurring in the body of the animal is the usefulness and balance of feeding. In this regard, the study of the effectiveness of the use of nutrients of the metabolic energy of diets to maintain the physiological needs of the organism of primates, the conversion processes in the body of growing animals, depending on feeding factors, is the most important. The obtained experimental data are of great importance for the compilation of scientifically based and optimally balanced diets of feeding, taking into account the true digestibility of feed. Which in turn allows you to optimally balance the feeding of all nutrients, while ensuring a reduction in the cost of feed and, as a result, increase the profitability of primates. It is shown that the introduction of biologically active additives into the composition of the ration provides an improvement in the process of feed assimilation and has a beneficial effect on blood counts in experimental monkeys.

Key words: digestibility, feed, blood, chlorella, additives, primates

Introduction. Biotransformation is the process of converting some organic compounds of biological raw materials into others under the influence of enzyme systems. This is a complex process consisting of mechanical, enzymatic and biological (microbial) processing of feed. Therefore, the assimilation of nutrients depends on many factors, among which are the species, breed, physiological condition, age-related characteristics of animals and the properties of the feed itself [1, 2].

Digestibility of feed should be understood as the body's ability to break down complex dietary substances (feed) into simpler ones under the action of enzymes of the gastrointestinal tract and microflora [2].

In the body, metabolic processes constantly digest feed nutrients, transfer them and incorporate them into the tissues of the animal's body, and the new substances are used not only to form new cells in the body, but also to renew old cells with even higher intensity. According to V.M. Gazdarova et al., Muscle protein is completely renewed in 10-15 days, Liver protein – in 3-4, body fat – in 10-18 days.

According to A. Sasson [3-10], biotransformation is extremely specific, since it deals with one type of reaction and with compounds of a certain structure. Chemically bound energy contained in the nutrients of the feed enters the animal body. Most of it in the growing body is deposited in the form of chemically bound product energy (muscles and so on), the rest is lost from the body in the process of life. After 10-13 days. In the body, energy is renewed, i.e. every two weeks, the body is almost completely rebuilt [6]. In this regard, the accurate determination of the conversion ratios of energy and feed protein into products is complicated by the body's expenses for updating its tissues. At the same time, one of the urgent problems at present is the provision of energy and protein nutrition for the country's population. The need for protein should be met, among other things, at the expense of animal feed [8].

The study of the effectiveness of the use of exchange energy for the synthesis of muscle and adipose tissue and conversion processes in the primates, depending on the nature of feeding, is timely and necessary [2].

Purpose of the study was to determine the digestibility and use of nutrients in diets with fishmeal, dry chlorella and dietary supplements in the form of Bactistatin and a suspension of chlorella on primates of the species macaca mulatta.

Materials and methods. To achieve this purpose, scientific research was conducted on male rhesus monkeys on the basis of the FGBNU NII Research Institute of Medical Primatology. For this, 5 groups of animals were formed at the age of 7 to 15 years, 5 animals per group, by the method of pairs of analogues by type, origin, age and physiological state, under conditions of cellular maintenance.

The work was carried out in accordance with generally accepted research methods [1, 7, 9].

Animal experiments were carried out in accordance with the requirements of the order of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation No. 267 of June 19, 2003 «On the approval of the rules of laboratory practice», orders of the Ministry of Health of the USSR No. 742 of November 13, 1984 «On the approval of the rules of work using experimental animals «and No. 48 dated January 23, 1985» On monitoring the performance of work using experimental animals «, ethical standards set forth in the Laboratory Practice Rules (GLP), Helsinki Declaration (2000) and European Directives Community 86 / 609EEC.

Rhesus monkeys were fed with full-feed combi feeds with nutrition calculated according to feeding standards [4, 9, 11]. The experimental design is presented in table 1.

Table 1 – Scheme of the experience on macaca mulatta

Groups	Number of animals	Feeding conditions
1. Control	5	Ration compound feed
2. Experienced	5	Ration compound feed + + suspension of chlorella – – 2,8 ml / kg W. m.
3. Experienced	5	Ration compound feed – – (14 % dry chlorella)
4. Experienced	5	Ration compound feed + + Battistinis 3 g / head
5. Experienced	5	Ration compound feed – – (18 % fish meal)

1-control group received a full-feed balanced feed.

The primates of experimental group 2, in addition to full feed, included a chlorella emulsion with a concentration of 60 million / ml in the amount of 2.8 ml / kg of live weight in the diet.

In experimental group 3, the following components were replaced by dry chlorella in the nutritional structure of the diet: milk powder by 90 %, egg powder by 9 %, and in the structure of the diet, chlorella was 14 %.

The primates of experimental group 4, in addition to complete feed, included a probiotic complex of bactistatin, manufactured by the Kraft group of companies, in the amount of 3 g / head per day as a prophylactic.

The following components were substituted for fishmeal in the diet of experimental group 5 for nutrition: skimmed milk powder by 100 %, sunflower

meal by 10.00 %, egg powder by 70 %, corn gluten by 2 %, in total, in the structure of the diet the sixth experimental group, fishmeal amounted to 18.26 %.

The health status and changes in homeostasis of primates, as a result of the inclusion of the studied feed and dietary supplements in the diet, were controlled by the results of hematological analyses. For this purpose, blood was collected before the primates were put to the test and after the experimental feeding was completed.

One head of the experimental animal was provided with a feed front-15-20 cm, and drinking was carried out from individual drinkers. Primates were kept in cell batteries, which made it possible to keep a careful record of feed intake and secretions in the physiological experience. The floor of the cage is made of galvanized mesh, through which feces freely falls. Under the mesh floor, there is a pull-out tray on which the feces were collected. The drinking bowl and feeder are installed on the outside of the cage.

The room was disinfected. After disinfection, the room is sanitized for 5 days before planting macaca mulatta.

The temperature in the vivarium was measured in the zone where the primates were located at various points, and it was +21-22 °C.

The speed of air movement in the room was 0.4 m / s, the amount of fresh air supplied to the vivarium was 5.5 M3/h per 1 kg of live weight.

Balance experiments were divided into two periods – preparatory and accounting.

The goal of the preparatory experiment (5 days) was to eliminate the influence of previous feeding and to accustom primates to the conditions of cellular maintenance.

During the accounting period (5 days), a thorough accounting of the consumed feed and excrement was carried out. The feeding schedule of primates in the experimental period was the same as in the control group.

The feces were collected daily at the same time (morning and evening), weighed and ground in a mortar. At each collection, 50 % of the homogenized mass was taken for analysis. The collected portions were stored in the refrigerator. After the end of the experimental (accounting) period in the collected feces, the initial moisture was determined by drying at 60-70 °C to a constant mass. The resulting air-dry mass was carefully ground and passed for analysis in a jar with a lapped cork.

Feed residues were also taken into account daily and an average sample was formed in the amount of 5 %, which was analyzed for the content of nutrients, since the content of nutrients in the feed residues does not correspond to their content in a given feed. The obtained data were used to calculate the total cost of feed and protein in General for the experiment.

During the research, the following indicators were taken into account: physiological and biochemical-chemical composition of feed, feces, (Pro-tein, fat, fiber, BEV, ash, calcium, phosphorus).

The results were processed statistically and expressed as arithmetic averages and their standard errors. The statistical significance of the differences was determined using a single-factor analysis of variance with subsequent a posteriori comparisons using the Dunnett method and the student's critical t-test. The differences were considered significant at the level of statistical significance $p < 0.05$.

Research results and discussion. Hematopoietic organs respond to various physiological and pathological effects on the body by changing the blood picture. Therefore, a blood test is of great diagnostic value.

To the results of our study, at the beginning of the experiment (table 2), the number of red blood cells in all the study groups was in the range of a slight increase relative to the physiological norm (5-6.2 million in 1 mm³), this pattern may be associated with an increase in the ambient temperature at the beginning of the experiment.

Table 2 – Hematological parameters of primates in the beginning of the experiment (X±SX)

Groups		1-c	2-e	3-e	4-e	5-e
Leukocyte (WBC), x109/1	5.5-13	9,82 ±1.65	12,60 ±0.99	11,26 ±0.89	11,40 ±1.14	11,48 ±1.55
Erythrocyte (RBC), x1012/1	5-6.2	6,30 ±0.05	6,31 ±0.18	6,76 ±0.32	6,45 ±0.24	6,14 ±0.39
Hemoglobin (HGB), g/l	110-145	143,40 ±1.40	144,80 ±6.14	145,20 ±5.04	143,00 ±1.41	135,20 ±9.20
Hematocrit (HCT), l/l	0.26-0.45	0,43 ±0.01	0,43 ±0.02	0,44 ±0.02	0,43 ±0.01	0,41 ±0.03
The average volume of erythrocyte (MCV), x10-15l	52-97	67,80 ±0.42	68,40 ±1.10	65,40 ±2.33	67,20 ±2.13	66,00 ±0.79
The average content of Hb in the erythrocyte (MCH)	18-33	22,76 ±0.29	22,92 ±0.46	21,60 ±0.89	22,28 ±0.79	21,98 ±0.36
Anisocytosis erythrocyte (RDW), %	11-16	12,98 ±0.20	13,26 ±0.35	13,18 ±0.31	12,74 ±0.31	13,40 ±0.29
Platelets (PLT), x109/1	200-400	308,40 ±18.15	417,60 ±23.22	357,20 ±47.30	392,00 ±21.32	291,60 ±47.81
Average platelet volume (MPV)	6-10	9,74 ±0.19	9,04 ±0.40	9,04 ±0.52	9,58 ±0.41	9,46 ±0.41
Sedimentation rate of erythrocytes, mm/h	0.5-5	0,89 ±0.11	1,10 ±0.11	1,10 ±0.27	0,90 ±0.12	0,80 ±0.14

There were no significant differences between the studied parameters in the control and experimental groups.

At the final stage of the experiment, the number of erythrocyte became closer to the reference indicators, which indicates the effectiveness of the use of dietary supplements in the experimental groups and is expressed in an increase in resistance (table 3). The main function of erythrocyte is respiratory, inextricably linked to the properties of the hemoglobin protein contained in them. A decrease in hemoglobin level is observed with unbalanced feeding, a deficiency in the diets of iron, copper, cobalt, protein, vitamin B12, folic acid, as well as with chronic intoxications and disorders of the gastrointestinal tract. The hemoglobin level decreases with secondary and alimentary osteodystrophy. In our experience, the results of the studies indicate that the level of hemoglobin in the blood, before the animals were tested, was within the physiological norm (table 2). Only in the 3rd group there was a slight increase in hemoglobin. This may be due to the above physiological increase in the concentration of erythrocyte in the blood. At the end of the experiment, the results of the analyzes showed that the hemoglobin level was within the reference indicators (table 3).

Table 3 – Hematological indicators of primates at the end of the experiment ($X \pm S_x$)

Groups		1-c	2-e	3-e	4-e	5-e
Leukocyte (WBC), x109/1	5.5-13	10,82 ±1.99	13,38 ±1.83	11,32 ±0.20	12,36 ±3.12	10,22 ±1.37
Erythrocyte (RBC), x1012/1	5-6.2	6,43 ±0.17	5,84 ±0.09	6,40 ±0.27	6,24 ±0.29	6,14 ±0.19
Hemoglobin (HGB), g/l	110-145	145,00 ±0.5	137,40 ±3.82	140,40 ±4.51	139,40 ±2.25	136.80 ±3.68
Hematocrit (HCT), l/l	0.26-0.45	0,43 ±0.00	0,41 ±0.01	0,42 ±0.01	0,42 ±0.01	0,41 ±0.01
The average volume of erythrocyte (MCV), x10-15l	52-97	68,20 ±0.42	69,80 ±0.96	66,00 ±2.12	68,00 ±2.50	67,20 ±0.82
The average content of Hb in the erythrocyte (MCH)	18-33	22,84 ±0.30	23,46 ±0.41	21,94 ±0.92	22,48 ±0.85	22,28 ±0.35
Anisocytosis erythrocyte (RDW), %	11-16	13,22 ±0.29	13,14 ±0.39	13,40 ±0.20	13,36 ±0.55	13,64 ±0.31
Platelets (PLT), x109/1	200-400	316,00 ±25.62	365,60 ±59.72	266,00 ±18.13	362,20 ±23.53	273.00 ±27.05
Average platelet volume (MPV)	6-10	9,94 ±0.33	9,76 ±0.34	10,12 ±0.64	9,94 ±0.53	9,96 ±0.49
Sedimentation rate of erythrocytes, mm/h	0.5-5	0,89 ±0.10	1,50 ±0.25	2,60 ±0.78	0,80 ±0.22	1,10 ±0.41

The level of leukocytes in the blood is very important. The concentration of these leukocytes directly affects the overall functioning of the immune system. This means that the level of leukocytes in the blood is able to indicate the degree of protection of the body as a whole. The manifestation of any malaise, any infection

is accompanied by a deviation of the indicator. In our experiment, the level of leukocytes was within the normal range, with the exception of the 2nd experimental group, which used a chlorella suspension, where at the end of the experiment there was a slight increase in them. This phenomenon may be of a natural physiological nature. An increase in the content of leukocytes is possible when the ambient temperature increases. This type of increase is reversible. In this case, leukocytosis can independently return to the normal range of values.

Platelets take an active part in blood coagulation and nonspecific defense reactions of the body. In our experiment, at the time of the beginning of the experiment, the platelet count in animals was within the range of reference indicators from 200 to 400 billion / l, with the exception of males of the 2nd experimental group (Table 2). In this group, there was a slight increase in platelets – by 17.60 billion / l, or 4.40 %, of the maximum allowable values of the reference indicators. The results of blood tests at the end of the experiment showed that in all experimental groups, as a result of the use of dietary supplements, the platelet count approached the physiological norm.

The rate of erythrocyte sedimentation depends on the size, volume, number of red blood cells, concentration of hemoglobin in the red blood cell, viscosity, and other factors. Experimental data show (tables 2 and 3) that the rate of erythrocyte sedimentation is within the normal range of 0.5-5.0 mm/h. A slight increase in the amount of hemoglobin, red blood cells and leukocytes, the level of hematocrit in the blood of monkeys of experimental groups to the upper limits of physiological norms may indicate that Chlorella, bactistatin stimulate erythropoiesis and leukopoiesis, without changing the stability of hematopoiesis and constancy in the composition and total number of peripheral blood.

The conducted hematological analyses indicate that all morphological and biochemical parameters after the use of dietary supplements and fish meal in the structures of the diet were close to the physiological norm by the end of the experiment, which, in turn, indicates a positive effect on the body and provides good growth and development of primates.

Daily accounting of feed consumed by animals and analysis of their chemical composition allowed us to determine the amount of nutrients consumed per day. Taking into account fecal matter and its chemical composition allowed us to determine the amount of digested nutrients and establish their digestibility coefficient (table 4).

Analysis of table 4 data indicates that the best results for the digestibility of most normalized organic substances were observed in primates of experimental groups. The digestibility of raw protein in experimental group 2 was higher by 4.18 %, in experimental group 3 by 6.83 % ($p < 0.01$). In the experimental group 4, where the drug Bactistatin was used as a probiotic, the protein digestibility coefficient, in relation to the control group, was higher by 0.97 %. In the

experimental group 5, where part of the feed was replaced with fish meal in the structure of the feeding diet, protein was absorbed by 5.66 % more effectively.

Table 4 – Digestibility of feed nutrients ($X \pm SX$), %

Digestibility	Groups				
	1-c	2-e	3-e	4-e	5-e
	Full-feed balanced feed	Suspension of chlorella	Dry chlorella	Battisti is	Fish meal
Protein	65,34±1,04	69,52±0,95	72,17±0,96**	66,31±2,08	71,00±1,14
Fat	38,09±0,98	42,79±0,79	40,70±0,87	39,80±2,51	42,01±1,85
Celluloses	25,88±1,01	30,02±0,90	30,66±1,12	23,15±1,79	30,13±1,26
Nitrogen-free extractive substances	78,05±1,12	79,90±2,03	82,20±2,03	78,94±1,91	80,31±1,27
Ashes	41,58±0,88	53,90±1,00	60,51±1,21	51,40±1,11	53,63±1,03
Calcium	44,37±1,94	53,66±1,58*	58,17±1,96	45,53±0,87	49,14±1,18
Phosphorus	59,79±2,01	60,51±1,61	67,86±3,12	59,98±0,31	61,00±1,84

Примечание: $p < 0.05^*$, $p < 0.01^{**}$.

The digestibility of raw fat was highest in experimental group 2 and in relation to the control group was higher by 4.7 %, in experimental group 3-by 2.61 %, in experimental group 4-by 1.71 %. In the primates of the experimental group 5, the digestibility coefficient was higher by 3.92 % in relation to the control.

There was a positive dynamic in the digestibility of raw fiber in experimental groups 2 and 3 by 4.14 % and 4.78 %. In the experimental group 5, it was 4.25 % higher than in the control group.

Nitrogen-free extractive substances of the feed were better absorbed by primates of the third experimental group by 4.15 %. Next in terms of assimilation of nitrogen-free extractive substances of the feed were primates of the 5th experimental group, the coefficient of digestibility is higher by 2.26 %. A similar pattern is observed in the 2nd and 4th experimental groups, the digestibility coefficients were higher by 1.85 and 0.89 % than in the control group.

Good indicators on the digestibility of raw ash were also noted in the experimental groups. As indicated in table 3, the digestibility coefficients were higher than in the control group by 12.32; 18.93; 9.82; 12.08 %.

The use of macronutrients calcium and phosphorus was higher in the experimental groups. Primates of the experimental group 2 better absorbed calcium by 9.29 %, and phosphorus – by 0.72 %. A similar pattern is observed for the rest of the experimental groups. Thus, primates of the experimental group 3 better absorbed calcium by 1.38 %, and phosphorus – by 8.07 %. In the primates of the experimental group 4, the coefficient of digestibility of calcium was 1.16 % higher,

and phosphorus – 0.19 %. In the experimental group 5, calcium was absorbed more efficiently by 4.77 %, and phosphorus-by 1.21 %

The use of biologically active additives in the form of probiotic and *Chlorella* suspension in the structures of complete Primate feed, as well as the replacement of part of standard feed with fish meal and powdered *Chlorella*, allowed to improve the biotransformation of feeding diets.

Conclusions. Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the inclusion of fish meal and dry *Chlorella* in the structure of Primate diets had a positive effect on the absorption of essential nutrients. The use of a biologically active additive in the form of a suspension of *Chlorella* and Bactistatin helped to stimulate the biotransformation of nutrients in the diet used in the nursery for feeding monkeys.

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